

A Study to Measure the Impact of E-Marketing (Digital) Among the Customers and Firms: A Case Study of the Hilton Hotel, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

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Abstract: The purpose of the study is to measure the impact of E-marketing (Digital) among the customers and firms to find out the awareness of digital marketing tools effectiveness in hotel business. E-marketing revealed that the customer are having strong sound of digital marketing and preferred to obtain services through digital channel. At present study made an attempt to explore the E-marketing is the new faces of technical tools are being used in recent business in worldwide. The aim of the study is to create and apply an effective e-marketing plan on Hilton's web site. Through this analysis, the company has used some basics marketing concepts in the website to be able to sustain in the business. This analysis is carried out the number of statistical customer is equal to 200 people that 132 of them were selected and surveyed as the statistical sample using Cochran's formula. The interviewees have been asked to sit on a face-to-face interview. The main tool used for collecting data is a closed questionnaire including the questions developed based on theoretical studies, the research conceptual model, and the quintuple Likert scale to survey the sample. Totally, the questionnaire includes few questions that some of them are related to the sales issue and of them are related to e marketing dimensions (14 questions about the use of internet for marketing activities related to the clients, 9 questions about the use of internet for marketing activities related to the distribution channels, and some questions about the use of internet for activities related to marketing research.

Keywords: E-marketing, information and communication technology, hotel industry.

1. Introduction

E marketing is the new face of marketing that is driving the total marketing technique in recent business world. Nowadays, business organizations especially the hotel businesses are facing lot of competition from the rivals and competitors. If the hotel businesses can build a marketing technique, which will deliver the objectives of the company and attract the customers more, then the achieving competitive advantage for the business will be more fruitful. In this regard e-marketing strategy can be a good platform. Marketing is about understanding Customers

social needs and wants. Nevertheless marketing creates relationship between a product and end use (Kotler 2006). Internet marketing is the way of process to create a relationship between customer through the online methods system and a process of building and maintaining customer relationships through online activities to facilitate the exchange of ideas, goods and services that satisfy the goals between company and customer. Individuals to carry the same meaning often use the terms e-marketing and Internet marketing. Initial investigations of the situation indicated the existence of a number of definitions for e marketing. As a result, the following definition was applied within the context of this study. "E-marketing explains company endeavors to notify buyers, communicate, promote and sell its offerings through means of the Internet" (Kotler and Keller 2009). The idea to investigate the impact of e-marketing business performance and the motivation to focus on a local tourism route was developed through the preliminary reading of existing literature, and informal discussions with local business managers within the field of tourism. Tsiotsou and Ratten (2010) identify e marketing and the use of new technologies as vital areas of future research within tourism marketing. They propose that due to the gaps in the literature, the focus of future research should examine the role of e marketing on the business performance of tourism. In their research project, Coetzee, Oldham, Schroenn, and Tang (2008) suggest that firms should endeavor to embrace new opportunities created by the development of new technology or face the threat of a decline in business. Discusses the research carried out in Bournemouth, England on rural accommodation businesses and their online marketing activities. He notes how important it was to utilize online marketing while competing to seek and retain customers Alford (2010).

Internet can be used for e-marketing purposes. E marketing is the modern way of communicating with the consumers through using the online media. The marketers try to spread the

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word of their products or services through Internet. The capabilities of the technologies and the Internet have expanded the chances of the becoming cost effective in the modern business world. Internet marketing ties the all-creative and technical manner of the organizations and it also includes the design, development, advertising and promotional activities. Internet marketing is totally different form the traditional marketing. The approach is basically, depends on the media of the advertising and promotions. The placement of the advertising in the Internet media come more often than in the traditional media. So, the use of Internet marketing should not be considered as an identical use of marketing [Kasper et al, 2006].

A. Background of the Study

For an enterprise to be effective and get better attention of the customers, it requires adopting comprehensive marketing techniques that will attract the customers most and deal with its ultimate destination to have strong customer base. A resilient consumer base comes up with substantial amount of advantages for an enterprise including the desired targeted customers and multiplied by sales increase and hence increases in the profit generation. That is why in the recent business world applying a unique marketing strategy is the ultimate goal of customer-oriented business which is why businesses seen to invest heavily in the attraction of the customers. Inspired to the same intention it is seen that other than the conventional marketing techniques organizations are seeking newer dimension of marketing strategies and one of those is e-marketing strategy. A main reason is for businesses to use e-marketing is that it accelerates the placing on the market and make a loop of dialogue or mass communication, interaction and dialogue not only to the request but by means of content, branding and with repeated stories (Peppers, et al., 2009). Contemporary marketing is focused on giving added value for the customers and the company. Modern marketing is to communicate with new generation or what is called the generation Z (Friedman, 2006). They are less loyal than ever before, because today's customers have more options than ever before (Nordstrom 2009). Today's customers seek more importance for them. So, companies need to update e-strategy, identify their target to hear and learn the behavior of the customers.

The establishment of the e-marketing web site is an investment (Angotti, 2011). Angotti (2011) has highlighted that e-commerce web sites require constants, news and update side-by-side with what customers are looking for. Inserting pages in e marketing begins a journey with the best information to current and potential customers. Promise to offer the best possible service at any time encourages the customer to remain for long-term (Angotti, 2011). It also opens for changes and new features that customers want then this have been successful (Angotti, 2011).

Current progress in the field of information technology, in particular in the Emarketing has brought about an affluent potential for a traditional company, which offer a wider product market (Buck et al., 2011). Travel agencies had formed lot of different websites in response to growing demand, which

provides hotel dwellers information about the products and services, e-marketing websites have a central role as an intermediary between companies and customers, as well as a channel for information and opportunities (Hossain, M. A., Wasantha, H. N., & Dissanayake, D. M. R. 2017 & Buck et al., 2011).

This research will focus on the current situation for the companies in the Malaysian hospitality industry and e marketing as a marketing tool. Hilton inn in Malaysia is particularly given the highlights in the subject of this research. This company offers a lot of facilities and a variety of shapes and sizes. Hotel dwellers from all over the world are interacted to the company by means of the e marketing that the company took for marketing. Tourists are now wanted and contemplate their needs to be fulfilled and with new services and products which should be changed and updated. Studies have shown that changes in the behavior of consumers and products is caused by e-marketing and the customers who have experience in e-marketing ultimately design for the tour by spending more than. E marketing and its impact on everyday life, as well as marketing are covered (Coupey, 2011).

For e-marketing model a generalization is discussed in detail. The most important sites for the search estimates hotel and important tasks after the e-commerce industry. E-commerce sites improvement in this project is examined to compare the stages of improvement of e-marketing strategy and the level of this shows the potentiality of the industry. This project shows the use of the state and enterprises, the development of emarketing websites for customers. Better overview of websites, e-marketing and continued targets and measures, in the research has been investigated. The research is approved a summary of the strategy for e marketing in the hospitality industry and see how with web analytics has turned into a powerful medium of rending of income. Using the results of the study in combination with e marketing, hotel business acceptance and realizing for the existing strategies is made. A summary of the main conclusions have been provided in the conclusions and recommendations which is the last concerns and considerations and questions about the results, including the unknown facts. Finally based on recommendations for further research have been delivered on these more interesting concept to other researchers or students. The marketing speed registered users around the world, as well as the dissemination of information and new scope for businesses to reach the customers. It is important to explain why it is an essential to build e-marketing strategy and that is to use the core of the presence of e marketing. Phases of development are considered as significant factors for the success of the offers and the use of e-marketing websites is common. E-marketing techniques and residents building techniques both in offline and online mode refer to the strengths and weaknesses of the activities in the hotel industry. E marketing introduces new strategy in marketing, which also provides for the production of the inhabitants on the pages of e-commerce (Doolin, et al., 2012). Web options and key performance indicators (KPI) are very significant elements in the strategy primarily on the success or failure of the marketing campaigns and other projects within the

framework of the e-business marketing presence (Law et al., 2010).

B. Hilton Hotel in Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

With more than 540 properties in 78 countries across six continents, Hilton Hotels & Resorts stands as the stylish, innovative leader in the full service segment. The flagship brand of Hilton Worldwide continues to build upon its legacy of innovation by developing products and services to meet the needs of tomorrow's savvy global Travellers while more than 144,000

Team Members shape experiences in which every guest feels cared for, value and respected the application process will begin. Your developer and our administration department will guide and assist you through the process. If you are converting an existing asset, the Product Improvement Plan (PIP), one of the most important parts of the approval process, is generated as a result of an extensive site inspection. All aspects of your hotel property will be evaluated and items will be identified that must be added or altered to bring the property in line with Hilton brand standards. Depending on your hotel property's size, location and condition, the time required from finalization of a Franchise License Agreement (FLA) to opening as a Hilton is a minimum of 90 days for conversion processes alone. Completion of PIP items in compliance with the contract may take significantly longer. If you are building a property, the Hilton Design and Construction Standards Manual will be your primary guide to a design that will result in compliance with the all brand standards (hilton.com).

Hilton Hotel was established in April 1987 under the Hilton International with the minor Hotel. These hotel operations began immediately with over 670 rooms and suites carefully designed for personal comfort and styles with several facilities for customer satisfaction. At the federal capital of Kuala Lumpur, in October 2005, the Transnational Corporation plc, bid to pay the sum of US 105million dollars to be able to get shareholder as partnership in the hotel, which was accepted by Hilton International. This made Transnational Corporation plc. to Have 51 % equity of the hotel properties. Since the hotel has opened its door in Malaysia, is still continues to be the choice for international and local events and meetings, for the government and individual bodies that can afford to pay for their Services Hilton Hotel services are comprised of the following: accommodation, Dining, services for corporate and private person.

20 Accommodations the rooms are deco-styles rooms and the suites are bright with creative artwork and large open windows that provide a good view of the city to the customers during their stay in the hotel. Also, the rooms are complete with desk, min chaise and marble bathrooms. The hotel has several different rooms for accommodations: Guest Rooms, Hilton Guest Room Plus, King Hilton Deluxe, and King Hilton Guest Room, king Hilton Guest Room Plus, King Royal Suite, and Twin Hilton Guest Room, suite Room, Deluxe and Executive Rooms. These rooms have the same names as other Hiltons in the world; they also have room facilities like rooms for disabled people, non-smoking rooms, individually controlled air

conditioning, mini-bar, tea-coffee making facilities, ironing and boards. Prices vary from each other depending on the room sizes and facilities. Dining Hilton Hotel provides continental meal for local and international businessmen and women. This continental meal is available in three areas of the hotels depending on the customer's choice for selection.

C. Research Objectives

The research has been driven on the following objectives:

- 1) To analyses the e-marketing tools used by Hilton Hotel.
- 2) To explore the e-marketing strategies are being used by Hilton Hotel.
- 3) To identify the hotel' e-marketing Mix.
- 4) To confer an effective e-marketing strategy.

D. Significance of the Study

The significance of e marketing is that from open stores or business, every type of business and their intension is increased sales and highlight brand awareness that a great marketing campaign can offer. Demystify the goals behind your marketing strategy with these 10 important benefits. The project discussed the topic of e marketing strategy improvement of a famous hotel in Malaysia. The focus was set on the improvement of e marketing for organizations other than associative marketing techniques. This thesis will point out the newer form of marketing techniques in light of its effectiveness and efficiency compared to associative marketing strategy. As a result in this section a sort discussion of the overall topic have been made. Along with this the key objectives of the thesis and scope of future perspective will also be discussed followed by a brief discussion of the company Hilton Inn Malaysia itself. Today's marketing is about building a cordial relationship between the company and their customers by understanding customer satisfaction. As a matter of fact, customer satisfaction usually keeps a value to the company image in the place of sales. The mission and vision of marketing is to keep the present customers for continuous growth while looking for new customers to purchase their product (Kotler 2004).

E. Problem Statement

The hotel industry faces a great challenge in the age of the information technology development. The traditional tourism hotel distribution channel faces a threat of the emerging IT or online environment. Throughout years the hotel industry was dependent on the intermediaries, who enabled the interaction between the suppliers and the customers. Nowadays, however, the suppliers can reach the customer directly via Internet having the geographical distance barriers and costs associated to them, disappeared. The Internet age changed the rapidly of the tourism distribution, enabling the entry of the new virtual intermediaries characterized by a strong competitive advantage towards other players of the sector. The internet allows a wide range of benefits for the companies and the customers, making the information widely available, reducing the difficulties in purchasing, marketing and distribution, allowing the sellers and the buyers to direct connect with each other. However, companies still face the difficulties on how to capture the

benefits in order to position themselves in the digital reality. The entry of the new customer intermediaries, known as the online travel agencies, introduced an innovative approach to the integration platform, collecting the suppliers and integrating them into a one stop-shopping place for the customers. The success of the platform depends however on the participation level of the tourism products suppliers. This raises the question of how to attract the various tourism suppliers to join the platform. The thesis presents a cost/benefit analysis of the joining the platform for every participant. The analysis considers the financial aspects of the decision, but also the intangibles, which should influence the long-term strategy for every hotel. The evaluation compares different distribution channels of the suppliers, both the traditional and emerging ones. The real life examples to support arguments presented are mostly based on the current world successfully improving Marketing can be a very simple concept and it has numerous different aspects to it. That is why the theoretical part of the thesis the problem creates only research marketing from a service company's point of view. The aim is to create a marketing plan for a hotel so it is important to find out how specifically a hotel can use marketing and what different marketing tools there are available to do so.

2. Literature Review

A. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction is a term rarely used in marketing. It is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or service to the customer expectation. The importance of customer satisfaction finalized when a firm has increased bargaining power. For example, hotel service holder plan providers, such as advertising, participate in a company that is demandable where only a few suppliers of a certain product or service exist. As such, many hotel provider plan contracts have a lot of room with provisions that they would never get away if there were, say, 100 special room and service providers, because customer satisfaction would be far too low, and customers would easily have the option of leaving for a better contract offer for a certain period. In any business satisfying the customer is the ultimate goal or objective of any marketer. Customer satisfaction service arises when a company or Hotel can provide customer with benefits that exceed customers' expectation and this is considered value-added. If customers are satisfied with the product or service which the company is providing then they will buy more, and do so more often. Customer gratification is an essential goal for each hotel providing customer services. The on-board experience is still something special for the customer. The customers have a wide choice to select the suitable hotel according to their requirements. Therefore, 10 hotel Companies are continuously working on the service and promotion development and innovation to differentiate themselves from their competitors. There are many factors that can help Hotel Company to build its customer base, and customer service and satisfaction can be a determining factor in the success of an entire operation. Customer satisfaction shows the independent variable of the

research. In the of hotel, the independent variables are the dimensions of electronic marketing including "the use of internet for marketing activities related to customer "the use of internet for marketing activities related to distribution channels", and "the use of internet for activities related to marketing research". Hotel also shows the components of each dimension as well as the dependent variable of the study of customer attraction. In this thesis need to focused on customer complaint and its quick resolution. In the hotel customer complains plays a vital role in customer satisfaction. There are 2 types of complain, controlled complaint are those which is under control such as fare related problems, worst services or misbehavior by staff, etc. and uncontrolled are those such as location or transport problems, technical issue, etc. So for solving these problems trained staff is required who can effectively minimize or handle these problems. The factor is that which influences on customer satisfaction. The most important thing is need to identified service provided, cleaning, safety these factors have an important role in customer satisfaction. There also found that customer satisfaction depends on personal entertainment, which is an important factor in staying room or private decisions of customer. According the study online room booking, call center facilities and reservation/cancellation is highest influencing factor in living decisions of the customer. Farris, Paul W.; Neil T. Bendle; Phillip E. Pfeifer; David J. Reibstein (2010).

1) *Technology and Online Information*

Information and online technology has penetrated many spheres of life and work. Recognizing the potential of this new technology, marketers have readily accepted and turned the marketing concept into e marketing. Technology online information shows the conceptual model of the research. In the role of hotel, the dependent variables are the dimensions of electronic marketing including "the use of internet for marketing activities related to customer and using modern technology "the use of internet for marketing activities related to technology which is giving more promotion for about hotel", and "the use of internet for activities related to marketing online research". The mode of hotel also shows the components of each dimension as well as the dependent variable of the study of customer attraction and using modern technology. There is no single direction of the concept of e marketing. Some authors emphasize the role of the Internet in the application of e marketing, while others perceive that term broadly, including the application of other information technology solutions.

2) *Perception and Attitude*

Hotel companies now face the challenge to execute brand and branding in the online context (Rowley, 2004). The role of the brand on the Internet has become complex, as customers now have greater control over marketing communication. Customer perception about hotel brand has been generated on the Internet especially when customers are searching for a hotel with which they are not familiar. Customer brand experience is determined by two channels — offline and online context — in different marketing communication forms such as magazines and e-newsletters. Companies need to ensure that consistent brand-image is maintained across these different channels (both

online and offline channels). Hotel perception and attitude is a Brand image is the mental picture of the product and service offering by a company. Hotel brand-image is now presented in both offline and online contexts, but empirical studies about the brand image perceptions of hotel customers in the online context are very limited, and there is a notable knowledge gap on factors that affect customer perceptions. Therefore, it is pertinent to investigate the factors that drive online brandimage from hotel customers' perspectives. In this paper, firstly we discuss online brand-image formation, and then, further to this, we elaborate upon the differences between offline and online brand-image to provide a conceptual framework for the study. Then, the paper significantly presents the factors that determine online brandimage from hotel customers' views based on semi-structured interviews and a scenario-based study. Finally, both academic and practical implications from the study are discussed in the conclusions. Perception and attitude is showing that hotel perception and attitude between customer satisfaction and technology online Information. There are the conceptual models of the research. In the role of hotel, the dependent variables are the dimensions of electronic marketing including "the use of internet for marketing activities related to the hotel perception and attitude "the use of internet for marketing activities related to perception which is giving more brand image for about hotel", and "the use of internet for activities related to marketing brand image". The mode of hotel also shows the components of each dimension as well as the dependent variable of the study of customer attraction Brand image of Hilton hotel perception and attitude. The 15 term "online brand-image" is new and it needs to be clearly defined. Traditionally, brand image can be considered as the combined effect of brand associations (attributes, benefits and attitude), brand personality and marketing communications held in the consumer's memory (Aaker, 1997; Biel, 1993; Keller, 1993; Park *et al.*, 1986).

3) *Service Delivery and Collecting Market Information*

In today's modern environment, excellent customer service is becoming the core competitive advantage in hotel industry. Meanwhile, many services are delivered by people in real time. People - customer-contact employees and those supporting them from behind the scenes - are critical to the success of any service organization (Wilson *et al.*, 2008). As within the models of service delivery and collecting market information presented by Guest (1987), Walton (1985) and Beer *et al.* (1984), frontline employees are viewed as the organization most important asset, being able of achieving and sustaining competitive advantage (cited in Kim Hoque, 2000, p.6). As a result, the hotel company should recognize the importance of its employees in representing and reinforcing the brand image of the company and delivering the service properly from the customer point of view. The service employees, who represent the organization in the customers' view, can have an impact on image and reputation of the company. When the service employees provide the proper service the customer's desires can be met, the company able to get a positive reputation hence attaining the higher markets share and the charge more than its competitors for service (Wilson *et al.*, 2008). The service

employees, who are knowledgeable, understanding, and concerned about the customers' needs, also influence the five dimensions of service quality: reliability, responsiveness, empathy, assurance, and tangibles (Wilson *et al.*, 2008). It is essential to understand and meet what the customer wants and needs with service employees' abilities to deliver (Wilson *et al.*, 2008). The Employees' Roles on Service Delivery. Grounded in this understanding of the importance of service employees and the nature of their roles in the organization, companies should pay more attention to knowing how to differentiate from their competitors and shaping service cultures and integrating appropriate strategic human resource management into service in order to delivering the good customer service through people. However, service employees often face interpersonal and inter organizational conflicts on the job. But actually sometimes the customer makes excessive demands which beyond the organization's rules. To summarize, the service employees not only need to follow the rules, but also need to accommodate the client requirements. But the conflict is greatest when the employee believes policies of the organization is wrong and must decide whether to satisfy the customer and risk losing a job, or to follow the policies. Therefore, the organizations should use strategies to create a flexible environment that helps front-line employees deal with the real problems on their job. These hotels have strong and well-developed customer-oriented service culture and highlight the employee satisfaction because they think employee satisfaction can influence customer satisfaction hence influencing the profitability of their hotels (Westin Hotels, 2010). Therefore, they would be good examples for us to explore how the hotels deliver good service quality by integrating the service culture and human resource strategies into the hotel. And we also research whether the hotels really are aware of the importance of the employees in service delivery. Service delivery and collecting market information showing that service delivery and marketing information between Customer Satisfaction shows the conceptual role of the research. In the role of hotel, the dependent variables are the proper service delivery and marketing information and dimensions of electronic marketing including "the use of internet for marketing activities related to customer "the use of internet for marketing activities related to distribution channels", and "the use of internet for activities related to marketing research". The mode of hotel also shows the components of each dimension as well as the dependent variable of the study of customer attraction giving service delivery to customer and which is related to the marketing information. (Wilson *et al.*, 2008, Hossain Md Amran 2017,2024)

4) *Service Quality*

The word service origins from the Latin word, Servitum that carries the meaning of served by slaves. Service is defined as an activity or a series of activities in intangible form, which usually takes place in interaction between customers and service providers. Some researchers further explained that service is an intangible benefit whose ownership could not be claimed, provided from one party to another. Generally, services are deeds, processes and performances (Salifu, Decaro,

Evans, Hobbs, Hossain Md, Amran & Iyer, 2010 & 2023). Quality is defined as the consumer's overall impression of the relative inferiority or superiority of the companies and its services (Siddique, Karim & Rahman, 2011). Besides that the quality could also be defined as a measure of the extent to which the service delivered fulfills the customers' expectations. Overall, quality refers to excellence, value, conformance to specifications, conformance to requirements, and loss avoidance (Chinh & Anh, 2008). Service quality means a customer's judgment about a service (Culiberg & Rojsek, 2010). Perceived service quality exists when customers make comparison between their expectations and perceptions of the service actually provided by vendors (Siddique, Karim & Rahman, 2011, Hossain, Amran 2023). In addition, the definition of service quality could be further expanded as the overall assessment of a specific service that results from comparing that firm's performance with the customer's general expectations of how firms in that industry should perform (Hossain, M. A., Hossen, M. S., Ahad, A., & Wasantha, H. N, 2024, Lo, Osman, Ramayah & Rahim, 2010). Perceived service quality is an essential element in high involvement industries especially hotel services. In fact, quality is one of the three important indexes of companies' performance, which consist of costs, productivity and quality (Hossain, A. 2023, Salifu, Decaro, Evans, Hobbs & Iyer, 2010). In older days, hotel service quality was used to be measured in terms of technical supports. However, as the hotel-undergone revolution, electronic hotel service has redefined the nature of customer relationship. Hotel services could no longer rely only on technical supports as a differentiating factor, personal supports are of more important because technical services are highly standardized. As a consequence, it is crucial to study the means of measuring and assessing service quality provided by promotion and advertising institutions when they adapt to the hotel and area environment changes. Analysis of the service component of hotel in a developing customer services as high-value information to hotel in other countries (Angur, Natarajan & Jahera, 1999). Numerous models have been developed in an attempt to measure the concept of service quality. SERVQUAL, which was developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml & Berry (1985) is among the most popular instruments used for evaluation of service 18 quality (Lo, Osman, Ramayah & Rahim, 2010). Parasuraman, Zeithaml & Berry (1985) first introduced a list of ten determinants of service quality. These determinants consist of access, communication, competence, courtesy, credibility, reliability, responsiveness, safety, understanding and tangibles. Parasuraman, Zeithaml & Berry's (1985) work was further supported and made reference by other researchers subsequently. It later consolidated them into five dimensions SERVQUAL, which include (1) tangibility, (2) authenticity, (3) responsiveness, (4) assurance and (5) empathy (Siddique, Karim & Rahman, 2011). Based on the five dimensions, a survey instrument for evaluating service quality was developed (Lo, Osman, Ramayah & Rahim, 2010). Firstly, tangibility refers to appearance of a service firm's facilities, employees, equipment, and communication materials. Lastly, empathy refers to the willingness and capability to provide

personalized attention to a customer (Culiberg & Rojsek, 2010). There were some studies performed by other researchers who did not support the model above. Finn & Lamb (1991) discovered that the five dimensions were inadequate to cover quality in a retail setting and doubted whether they are generic. Cronin & Taylor (1992) also expressed criticism on the model. Although there was some opposition to the SERVQUAL instrument, it is widely used for confirmatory factor analysis. In addition, SERVQUAL was proven to be the most economical model that was adopted in various service organizations to measure service quality including hotel (Lo, Osman, Ramayah & Rahim, 2010).

B. Review of Researches on Customer Satisfaction

Among the most popular studies on service quality is the qualitative study performed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1985). Based on the focus group interviews with consumers and executives, service quality model was proposed. There were five gaps identified respectively for each group of respondents in the proposed model. On top of that, criteria in evaluating service quality were classified into ten service quality determinants, which include reliability, responsiveness, competency, access, courtesy, communication, credibility, security, understanding, and lastly tangibles. Later, the 19 instrument known as SERVQUAL was developed to measure service quality and the ten determinants were further consolidated into five dimensions which consist of tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (Parasuraman, Zeithaml & Berry, 1985). Bontis, Booker and Serenko (2007) conducted research to understand the mediating effect of organizational reputation on customer loyalty. The results indicated that there is an important relationship between organizational reputation and customer loyalty. The findings also substantiated the widely accepted theory, which advocated the link between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Different researchers had embedded various elements in their studies for relationship marketing. Some researchers identified reliance, communications, mutual values, sympathy and reciprocal attempt as the most significant components of relationship marketing (Aaltonen, 2004). On the other hand, some other researchers had introduced three categories of variables as relationship marketing foundation for hotel industry which includes financial connection, social connection and structural connection (Aaltonen, 2004). Rashid (2003) introduced commitment, communications, social relations, reliance, sympathy, positive experiences and fulfilling commitment as primary elements which form relationship marketing. Later in year 2007 some researchers further reduced the elements to four, which are reliance, commitment, communication and confliction control (Aaltonen, 2004). Relationship marketing theory advocates the essential creation of a long term and sustainable business relationship between customers and service providers. Requirements for service providers are to build trust with their respective customer and to exhibit commitment towards ensuring a long lasting and strong relationship in order to be competitive and sustainable in the industry. Trust and commitment are nurtured on the basic

understanding of customers' expectations, requirements, needs, wants and also specifications (Morgan & Hunt, 1994).

1) Review of Customer Satisfaction Models

There are various customer satisfaction models developed. The first model discussed is the traditional macro-model of customer satisfaction. According to this model, perceived performance is always different from objective or technical performance when customers feel unfamiliar with some products or services, which are 20 complicated and intangible. Comparison standards vary among individual, situation and product or service. Perceived disconfirmation could be defined as the evaluation of perceived performance based on comparison standards (Hom, 2000). The second model discussed is the model of linkage of customer value chain to customer satisfaction. This model proposes the concept of value as a driving force in product choice and the relationship between value and satisfaction as a brief psychological reaction to a component of a value chain. The third model discussed is the Model of Two Levels of Satisfaction and Perceived Service Quality. This model supports the conceptualization of perceived quality as a separate construct, distinct from satisfaction. In addition, it highlights the construct of a "global" level of satisfaction (the overall service satisfaction) as opposed to the construct of a component level of satisfaction (the encounter service satisfaction) by Hom, 2000.

H1. There is positive relationship between technology and customer satisfaction

H2. There is positive relationship between perception and customer satisfaction

H3. There is positive relationship between service delivery or collecting market information and customer satisfaction

H4. There is positive relationship between customer's decisions regarding choosing the airlines to travel.

Fig. 1. Theoretical framework of the study

C. Meaning of Variables

A characteristic, number, or quantity that increases or decreases over time, or takes different values in different situations is called variable

There are two basic types of variable these are,

1. Independent variable: that can take different values and can cause corresponding changes in other variables.
2. Dependent variable: that can take different values only in response to an independent variable.

According to the Hypothesis the details of variable,

- 1) Customer satisfaction: customer satisfaction is an independent variable because e marketing planning is based on hotel and customer proper satisfaction.
- 2) Technology and online information: Technology and online is a dependent variable because in a hotel the main target is customer satisfaction according to the customer satisfaction need to utilize or using proper technology and online information.
- 3) Perception and attitude: Perception and attitude is depend on customer so it is a dependent variable.
- 4) Service delivery and collecting market information: Service delivery and collecting market information is also depend for the customer so it is a dependent variable
- 5) Service Quality: Service delivery is depend on customer so it is a dependent variable.

3. Research Results

A. Method and Data Collection

For this research the top-level customers has been selected by a simple random sampling technique. The sample has been selected at the convenience of the researcher about 200 people from that 132 were selected as the statistical sampling using Cochran's formula. Secondly the interview has been asked to sit on a face-to-face interview. Prior to the interview they have been informed of the maintenance of confidentiality of their identity and they have been sent a consent form. The quintuple Likert scale of questionnaire developed based on the theoretical studies and few of the questions are related to the sales and others are related to E-marketing dimensions (14 questions about the use of internet for marketing activities related to the clients, 9 questions about the use of internet for marketing activities related to the distribution channels, and some questions about the use of internet for activities related to marketing research.

B. Analysis of the E-marketing Platform of the Hilton Hotel

The importance of the E-marketing has been asking from the customers whether it's important of not and to put forward of their perception regarding the importance of the e-marketing platform for the company. The questions were confined to the actualization and importance of the development of e-marketing strategy and platform for the company. The response of the customers has been shown in the figure.

Fig. 2. Requirement of e-marketing platform
Source: The interview response of the customer

From the response of the customer it can be seen that 80% (8 of the 10 customer) of the customers think that e-marketing platform is important for them. On the other hand two others (20%) of the customer think otherwise. The researcher from the literature review found that in terms of the e-marketing platform of a company works as a gateway for the customers and that is the reason why it has to be pertinent, attractive and prepared. And that is the reason why most of the supervisor agrees in developing the e-marketing platform for the company. The researcher also views that in term of Hilton with the e-marketing platform the company provides the customers information of the company and along with this the e-marketing platform works as a window for discovering the product lines the company have which is shown below.

In this explanation the importance of the e-marketing platform the researcher has come to know that, the managers and the superior authority of the company wants to develop an e-marketing platform for e-commerce and brochure on the same page. Brochure on the e-marketing platform displays the product range of the company and presence on the e-marketing platforms is working as a version of the online business plan. On the other side, page booklet with e-marketing platforms bring a sense of reliability and credibility of customers and gives useful information such as contacts of the company with operating hours in details. According to the management, customers can purchase the item online through the e-commerce site of the company. The supervisor of the company further publish the budget for the research of the company which has taken is not such high yet it is based on the value of the site, the higher authority of the company has decided to outsource this researcher from some of the renowned web design company from the foreign countries. For this the hotel company has decided that the e-marketing platform would be outsourced from some of the subcontinent region such as from Asia where build this type of e-marketing platform is not much costly. The Customer of the hotel believes that the new look will bring something new experience for the customers and they will feel that the site meets your expectations.

C. Design of the E-marketing Platform

The researcher needs to ask the respondents to put their perception regarding the e-marketing platform of the company. The researcher also need to ask them to put forward of their thinking regarding the context, color, design, pattern, and other relevant things of the e-marketing platform for the company. In fact they have revealed several aspects of the design of the e-marketing platform of the company. The response of this survey need to explain them by all in details to the company supervisor as much care as social media marketing is obedient these days, it's nowhere close to replacing good old fashioned email as a means to reach current and potential customers. With so many services out there for customers and it's not always easy to know which one is right for your business.

1) The interview response between supervisor and the customer

From the response of the customers it can be seen that, most of the customer think that the e-marketing platform has good

color and context. On the other hand most of the customer thinks otherwise. Apart from this, the response from customer shows that most of the customer thinks that the format of the e-marketing platform is very good. Whereas from the response of the supervisor, it can be seen that least of the customer thinks that e-marketing platform should be developed on a good platform. On the other hand few of the customers think otherwise. Along with this the response of the supervisor reveals that, minimum number of the customers thinks that the presentation of the e-marketing platform of the company is not much good. On the other side a few number of the customer think it will be more useful. Last but not in the least the, supervisor ask to their perception regarding the graphics of the e-marketing platform of the company. And from the response of the supervisor it can be seen that a few percent of the customer think that the graphics of the e-marketing platform of the company is quite good. Only fewer of the customers think otherwise.

The supervisor publish the first consideration for the search engine is the design of the site As it can be seen in the following image presentation is not pleasant, and it is old and outdated which is also supported by the customer. But it is precisely developed as the menu system is set on the left of the e-marketing platform as the researcher views. The researcher also shows that the site is not in the correct format, as the title of the webpage is not with clear message. The visual effect such as color for the text and font style is not compatible, but attempt has been taken to improve the Hilton site. It is a good site, with good graphics and quotations however for the new customers or visitors it can create confusion for them. The e-marketing platform of Hilton is designed through flash programming (in most cases except the main page) with the gallery of the e-marketing platform is beautifully designed. Generally, the e-marketing platforms that are designed using flash delivers attractive and concise message. Moreover, the dynamics of this type of e-marketing platform is not an easy task even in case of some developers needs to make changes. Under this viewpoint these types of e-marketing platforms are not profitable. Because of the same reason even in case of SEO this type of e-marketing platforms are not easily found in the online and therefore the ranking of this type of e-marketing platforms get poor in Google as well. The Hilton is both international and national customers operating in different language may not be possible for the company in many cases. This is because of the different reason as mentioned above. The public expects the design of an e-marketing platform to be simple, easy-to-read and pertinent so that they can easily navigate through the e-marketing platform and understand the context of the e-marketing platform together with clear company message as well. The Administration has proposed that the site should be easily accessible and can be opened in all sorts of platforms with which the majority of customers deal and they suggest to creating the e-marketing platform in that manner. The supervisor have come up with the solution that the site is intended to be a program of Word Press and can be opened in any application. As per their requirements there is also a separate shopping cart for separate destinations and regions.

Because of dealing with international customers the Hilton in its e-marketing platform offers six different languages including English and Malay language.

The site uses a fast and easily accessible option to the guests, which offers them surfing the products and offerings the promotions specifically. On the left side of the e-marketing platform the company has provided the options to choose their selective products and services of the company. On the other hand, on the top of the e-marketing platform the company has several options to choose from by the customers where the relative information of the company is provided.

D. Content of the E-marketing Platform

The advertising that the hotel company conducts is eye-catching. It is seen that the necessary tools of marketing at times fail to work the way it should be because of lack of content of the e-marketing platform and the development of the e-marketing platform will not be attractive and being at the top search will only be for a while. The researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding the content of the e-marketing platform of the company.

The interview response of the customer:

From the response of the customer it can be seen that the supervisor think that the content of the e-marketing platform of the company is quite rich. On the other hand the customer thinks negative. It has been highlighted from the response of the supervisor think that the content the ingredients of the e-marketing platform should be informative, useful, and valuable and also entertaining to attract to retain the audiences.

E. Meta tagging of the E-marketing Platform

The researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding the usage of Meta tagging by the e-marketing platform of the company. The response of the supervisor has been shown in the following figure:

Fig. 3. Perception of the customer regarding the Meta Tagging
Source: The interview response of the supervisor and customer

From the response of the supervisor, it can be seen that 100% (8 of the 10 customer) of the customer think that the e-marketing platform of the company uses the Meta tagging. The supervisor have describe that in terms of the tools of webmaster the e-marketing platforms which has meta-tags can inform the search engines about the e-marketing platforms. They have also said that description of the contents of the fields to all types of customers can be provided with the help of it and each individual system can be treated to include only with the meta-tags and leaving the rest. The researcher views that the keywords meta-tags are no longer necessary in Google but

adapted to other search engines. Meta is the element that search engines take into account, when people and customers visit the site. Keywords must be properly in place be packed townscape is summarized in the title of this pages. Keywords are the target labels, and especially when checking out, the content of the webpage, marked with the destination.

F. Search Engine Optimization (SEO) of the E-marketing Platform

After that the researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding the usage of Search Engine Optimization (SEO) by the e-marketing platform of this hotel company. The response of the supervisor of the hotel has been shown in the figure.

Fig. 4. Perception of the supervisors regarding the SEO
Source: The interview response of the supervisor and customer

From the response of the supervisor it can be seen that 100% (8 of the 10 customers) of the customers think that the e-marketing platform of the company uses the Search Engine Optimization [SEO]. On the other side two others (20%) of the customer think opposite. From the literature, the researcher views that in terms of Monahan (2011) in the business world almost all the companies have their own e-marketing platforms, but hardly 5% have the knowledge of that usage of search engine optimization (SEO) for their marketing plan. Now the supervisors have urged that this search engine is a technology which comes with the Internet and the aim of finding information on the Internet. They also said that available materials could be the web pages with text, pictures and other files. In the interview with the supervisor and customer of marketing of Hilton it has been found that they seek their e-marketing platform to be at the top of Google as people hardly bother in scrolling down the web pages to find out the desired one. Also, they mentioned that most of the time the product is offered to the channels rather than the company directly because the client does not find the site in Google (hilton.com.my).

G. Navigation of the E-marketing platform

After that the researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding the usage of navigation system that is used in the e-marketing platform of the company. The response of the mangers has been shown in the figure.

Fig. 5. Perception of the supervisors regarding the navigation of the e-marketing

Source: The interview response of the supervisor and customer

From the response of the supervisor it can be seen that 80% (8 of the 10 customers) of the customers think that the navigation system that is used in the e-marketing platform of the Hotel Company is quite good. On the other hand one (20%) of the customers thinks that the navigation system that is used in the e-marketing platform of the company is moderate. Based on the literature the researcher views that navigation can be so versatile or can be simple or complex: with one important pages, a layer of the platform with different content for registered users, and one for members with the information of the product and so on. The researcher also views that between of rugged services depending on the operational principles and procedures work differently navigation principal can be of different types and categories. Navigation has to be more and more graphical, so that customer can but read the whole thing to get insight with almost the absolute positioning of menu item from the menu of the content of the content displayed by means of JavaScript (Smashing Media, 2012).

H. Analysis of the e-marketing advertising of the company

From the literature the researcher views that according to e-marketing platform advertisement can be done in the following manners. Disbursements of time with a simple search engine optimization strategies. The researcher also views that usage of rich content for the e-marketing platform is required so that it become appealing to the eye of the viewers. Attempts to be taken to institutionalize the Meta tags. Send URL of the site to search engines. That is how most of the visitors can so figure out the e-marketing platform and the more they come the more the company will be benefited. The company can design its company cards by which advertising the company and the site will be a great thing. Send press release to the web page, if it deserves a story. Maybe even coverage in news sources online will jump high only if the content is unique. The company can use different types of T-shirts, stickers, pins and other advertising materials on the e-marketing platform and the name of the URL. The supervisor has suggested obtaining backlinks and this works as a reference or an active link from other sites to the site of the company. They have also urged that use of social-networking sites like Twitter, Facebook and MySpace can be quite a revolutionary idea with the help of various newspapers Hilton has advertised its Web pages. The best way to be created to promote the company in the online arena is to have a good ranking in Google and other search engines by the

site of the company. Hence, the managers have urged that in addition to the above the company has used back kinship and Facebook, to promote the e-marketing platform of the company (Braniac, 2012).

The researcher views that Hilton for a PPC campaign uses the keyword analysis tool of Google. Due to this Hilton is suggested to check different thing, which is the same as for recipients that gives a range of factors to the users at every step of the research process to find out how they found the pages of search engines in a PPC campaign planning. The researcher also views that almost similar keywords are given so that the visitors can have the keywords with Google keyword check tools, what was introduced as additional keywords. This tool shows the average and the estimated average campaign, CPC or the cost per click with using the PPC (Braniac, 2012).

I. E-mail Marketing of the E-Marketing Platform

The researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding the usage of e-mail marketing for e-marketing platform of the company. The response of the mangers has been shown in the figure.

Fig. 6. Perception of the supervisor regarding e-mail marketing

Source: The interview response of the supervisor and customer

From the response of the supervisor it can be seen that 90% (9 of the 10 customers) of the customers think that the e-marketing platform of the company is required to use the e-mail marketing. On the other hand one (10%) of the customers thinks otherwise. From the literature the researcher views that has suggested that the sending of email has seen remarkable increase over the years and this has upsurge the number from 5.1 million per day in the year 2005 to 135 million, with this it show the potentiality of email marketing and if the company has used the correct number of E-mail messages From the response derived from the interview with the management of the company the researcher came to know that the company is using the e-mail marketing campaign but not as effectively as it should be. Because it was impossible to acquire a customer database earlier and it is very difficult to know whom the buying behavior of the customers. According to the response of the customer the online site can be used for the customers to show the product line and product offering of the company. Email marketing can be used to assess the customer loyalty and generate traffic to the e-marketing platform with the help of the related email communication (Chaffey, 2007).

J. Adequate budget for the e-marketing platform

The researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding whether the Company has adequate

budget for the e-marketing platform of the company or not. The response of the supervisor has been shown in the following figure:

Fig. 7. Perception of the supervisors regarding the budget of the e-marketing

Source: The interview response of the supervisor and customers

From the response of the supervisor it can be seen that 100% (10 of the 10 customers) of the customers think that the company has adequate budget for the e-marketing platform of the company. From the literature the researcher views that for a company to be successful in online marketing campaign the company should make the best use of the strategy that the company has undertaken. The supervisor have disclosed that for this it has to have proper and adequate budget for the smooth operation of the platform For Hilton in 2016 the following budget has been undertaken for the design of the e-marketing platform and the marketing (hilton.com.my).

K. Control of the E-marketing Platform

From the literature the researcher views that part of the marketing plan can be reached through a combination of traditional techniques such as marketing activities research, market research and analysis of the clients and innovative techniques such as webserver logs, using technology to achieve the objectives of the company The supervisor of the company has disclosed that the company for this use simple technique which in large scale catches the attention of the user and eventually the company is in a better ranking on Google for SEO. The supervisor suggests that Google can generate more clicks, which should be another method of advertising. The researcher views that Google Analytics report suggests that the company has the possibility to check whether changes to make to respond to the core objectives of such marketing (Chaffey, 2007).

L. Analysis of the Web Analytics of the Company

Fig. 8. Perception of the supervisors regarding the web analytics

Source: The interview response of the supervisor and customer

The researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding the usage of Web analytics by the e-marketing platform of the company. The response of the supervisor has been shown in the figure.

From the response of the supervisor it can be seen that 100% (10 of the 10 customers) of the customers think that the e-marketing platform of the company uses the web analytics. Hilton earlier used different types of web Analytics, but at present the company uses no web analytics. However the customers have urged to use Google analytics as according to them it can track the user activity of Hilton. They have also said that PPC advertising through Google Analytics can be done and with some other options as mentioned earlier. From the response of the customers it is found that Hilton to track the visitors of the e-marketing platform has lacking and another thing is that the company hardly seen to use social media accounts. The managers urged to make that small change at this time, as this can be a crucial factor for the company as Facebook pages can be used to promote the product of the company (hilton.com.my).

M. Profile of site visiting of the E-marketing Platform

The researcher has asked the respondent to put forth their perception regarding whether the company has profile of site visiting people of the e-marketing platform of the company or not. The response of the supervisor has been shown in the figure.

Fig. 9. Perception of the supervisors regarding the profile of site visiting people

Source: The interview response of the supervisor and customer

From the response of the supervisors it can be seen that 100% (10 of the 10 customers) of the customers think that the e-marketing platform of the company has the profile of site visiting people. The researcher views that the Hilton in e-marketing platform uses the site visiting profile which eventually tracks who visited the e-marketing platform of the company, how they are delivered their services and at what time of the day they have made their visit to the site. They also urged that this provides valuable information to the organization, which will also help with an email and can give a product-marketing company to promote its products and offers in a large scale (hilton.com.my).

N. Situation analysis of Hilton

As per table 1, it indicates five variables average responses

from customers regarding the e-marketing system in Hilton restaurants in Malaysia. Based on the analysis, it found under the online information, there are three questionnaire can be seen, its average 80% that mean there is positive relationship with customer satisfaction, hence here null hypothesis has rejected alternative hypothesis accepted because their average level is more than 0.5 that has shown strong relationship between online information and customer satisfaction.

Table 1
variables average responses from customers

Variable	Yes	No
Online Information	80%	20%
Perception and Attitude	90%	10%
Service Delivery and collecting market Information	20%	80%
Service Quality	90%	10%
Customer Satisfaction	60%	40%
Total	340%	160%
Total: Yes 68% and No 32%		

As per table 1, it indicates five variables average responses from customers regarding the e-marketing system in Hilton restaurants in Malaysia. Based on the analysis, it found under the online information, there are three questionnaire can be seen, its average 90% that mean there is positive relationship with customer satisfaction, hence here null hypothesis has rejected alternative hypothesis accepted because their average level is more than 0.5 that has shown strong relationship between online information and customer satisfaction.

As per table 1, it indicates five variables average responses from customers regarding the e-marketing system in Hilton restaurants in Malaysia. Based on the analysis, it found under the online information, there are two questionnaire can be seen, its average 20% that mean there is negative relationship with customer satisfaction, hence here null hypothesis has accepted alternative hypothesis rejected because their average level is less than 0.5 that has shown poor relationship between online information and customer satisfaction.

As per table 1, it indicates five variables average responses from customers regarding the e-marketing system in Hilton restaurants in Malaysia. Based on the analysis, it found under the online information, there are four questionnaire can be seen, its average 90% that mean there is positive relationship with customer satisfaction, hence here null hypothesis has rejected alternative hypothesis accepted because their average level is more than 0.5 that has shown strong relationship between online information and customer satisfaction

As per table 1, it indicates five variables average responses from customers regarding the e-marketing system in Hilton restaurants in Malaysia. Based on the analysis, it found under the online information, there are three questionnaire can be seen, its average 60% that mean there is positive relationship with customer satisfaction, hence here null hypothesis has rejected alternative hypothesis accepted because their average level is more than 0.5 that has shown a good relationship between online information and customer satisfaction

1) *Analysis of the Competitors of Hilton*

The base product of the company is hotel rooms and food in the Hilton in restaurants, although it sold a different other

product related to hotels and restaurants. The nearest competitors for the company are as follows:

Table 2
Competitors of Hilton

Competitors
Accor SA
Days Inns Worldwide, Inc.
Travelodge Hotels Ltd.

There are other competitors, which sell similar products relating to hotels and restaurants. From them the company also faces a major challenge.

2) *SWOT Analysis of Hilton*

<p>STRENGTH</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing customer base. Quality products yet reasonable price. Existing distribution. 	<p>WEAKNESS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Technology/ poor IT skills and web experience. Don't have online partners. Customer tracking is not available.
<p>OPPORTUNITIES</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Still large demand of hotels and restaurants in UK and in Europe. 	<p>THREATS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Big companies that are in same business. Cheap product distributor

Fig. 10. SWOT analysis of Hilton

O. *Product and Services of Hilton*

Hilton offers the customers with products of dwelling in the rooms of the hotel and taking different food in the restaurants. Hilton currently sells products on diversified markets around the world. It covers almost 60% of the Malaysian markets and executives believe that as the company is no longer growing on the domestic market, it is necessary to focus on other markets. In 2006 it announced a joint venture agreement with the Asian groups. This is the first step to expand the brand outside the Malaysia. Room rates are expected to be in the region of RM 350 or USD 400. Hilton is largest international hotel market conglomeration of the company, after the joint venture with Asian company, which was announced in 2010. An equity investment of up to RM 900 million will be invested in the next 10 years in the joint venture, which will consist of 50% shares and expected to opening 80hotels respectively 12000 rooms for business.

4. Findings and Conclusion

A. *Research Findings*

For finding this answer for the research questions from the analysis it has been referred to different textbooks and also different earlier researches performed in this topic. To find out the actual problems the author has taken one to one interview with the chairpersons of the company. Also took suggestion what company director want in their new website and applied accordingly in the development of new e-marketing platform.

B. *Findings*

From the analysis it has been found that website is important to any company to show the existence of any business. Website

is the first place when someone looks for the information about any business. Furthermore, website allows for a much more robust experience for visitors than most other platforms. This means that company can be more efficient at providing visitors the information that they're looking for, as well as the opportunity to create web applications for more value to your visitors. Through Research and from the analysis it has been found that today almost all corporate have their own website designs that market their companies and also establish their online identity. In order to reach out to wider audiences around the world, corporate website should be appealing with all advanced features. In the presence of innumerable corporate e-marketing platform on the Internet, customers have gone very selective and prefer only those e-marketing platforms that are real eye-candy. Research also shows that the most informative and easy to use site can attract and keep the visitors for long time. Content should be correct and interesting to read. Most of the customers often seek for flawless and rich content that can convince them to buy products. Therefore, attention needs to be paid while writing content for website, as it is an essential tool. Therefore, companies should rightly consider a Corporate Web design company which offers the best custom website designs at affordable prices. The role of a corporate web design company is vital to attract customers to your website. Besides, it also takes care of all the essential requirements for website designing. According to the research the first place people go to find some information are the search engines like Google, yahoo, Bing etc. To be listed on the top of the search engines means to have more visitors on the web site. The most easy and common way to make the site visible on the Google are paid advertisement like PPC, Ad word, banner ads etc. But through effective SEO sites can be easily visible in Google. Research found that Company can use Google analytics to track the customer. It is complex but provides more information about where your clicks are coming from. It's ideal if companies are interested in the entire flow of customers through site, not just conversions. It can include conversions from non-ad Words sources, so it's a great comparison tool. From the analysis it has been found that through PPC ad targeted traffic is attracted to the website based on the keywords selected by company for marketing campaign so keywords need to be selected precisely. Through good search engine optimization and PPC ad effective search engine marketing can be done which means effective e marketing can be done. From the analysis it has been found during the research process email marketing helps companies to:

- 1) Target customers.
- 2) Provide information about the company, products and offer.
- 3) To build Customer relationships, loyalty and trust.
- 4) Supports sales through other channels.

From the research on questions on how to increase traffic to the sites and convert visitor to customer from the analysis it has been found that through the effect SEO and with the help of Google ad campaign companies can increase traffic to their site. To keep the visitor the contents of the website should be interesting and companies should offer always new thing to the

visitors. In ecommerce site payment process should be easy most of the customers leave the site due to difficulties in the payment. Sites need to be trustworthy to turn visitors to customers. Poor site performance is a major cause of customer dissatisfaction. In addition to speedy functionality, the site design and content also impact consumer perceptions of the company and its products. A well performing and informative website can be a powerful marketing tool. From the analysis it has been found that the cost of e marketing is difficult to estimate, the budget depends upon how much the company wants to invest on the marketing campaign, web site development search engine optimizations other ad campaigns. Hilton hotel budget is presented in 4.6. Through the research the most challenging factor for e marketing is to deal with technology and IT. As in the case companies, they do not have skilled IT professionals who can keep all the details of company products up to date. Another challenges is to deal with the high transparency of product and price, buyer have now power they can compare the price and products of competitor within a click. Also security is the most important factors while we talk about ecommerce the site should be trust worthy which makes e-marketing challenging. Although e marketing enables companies to check how many hits and visits they receive to the website, companies are not able to monitor how many of these visits are sales hence this can be considered as challenges in e marketing.

C. Limitation of the Study

During the development of the research, there were still some difficulties and problems come in the way. E-marketing has broad definition, its marketing done through any electronic means. In this research from the analysis it has been is more focused in the development and marketing of e-marketing platform. The research only tells about marketing website; how the website can be visible in different search engines like Google as most of the companies now find information through Google search engines. Search engine optimization is a vast topic and there are hundreds of things that matters in effective SEO the basic and most important topic are covered in this research. Secondly, this research is also the development project due to the time limitation from the analysis it has been couldn't present all the progress report during the development.

D. Recommendations

It seems that the e-marketing strategy or platform that the company has or required to build the company needs to have some considerations. So far these are the suggestions of the research as follows:

- 1) The e-marketing platform should be attractive to the customers with good context and eye-catching attributes.
- 2) The e-marketing strategy of the company should be developed in way that it becomes cost effective and efficient as well.
- 3) The company should consider the backup plan so that the strategy that is undertaken and the platform that is

going to be built by the company do not lose its purpose and context.

- 4) Prior to developing the strategy, a market survey can be conducted to know the perception of the people so that it can reflect the desire of the people.
- 5) The strategy or platform that is going to be developed for the e marketing should be well composed and developed using people-oriented tools and elements.
- 6) The strategy should be conducted in a way that the people can access the platform with ease.

E. Suggestion for the Future Researchers

This research is a study of e-marketing plan for the Hilton's website. From the analysis few suggestions have been derived for future researchers, which have been formed after the research and analyses. Firstly, through strategic e-marketing plans and customer segmentation in other European Countries would be in the company's best interest as it has few opportunities to grow any more in domestic markets. Secondly, for the marketing plans to be developed in other European countries new market researches will have to be conducted, especially in customer and competitor analysis. The differences of market situation and macro-environment are necessary to keep in mind. Thirdly, companies that are engaged in international markets need a systematic method to develop a strategic marketing plan in foreign countries, which would be an interesting and practical topic.

F. Conclusion

The research has been performed for the case company Hilton, but other company who are in online business can be benefited from this research. The aim of the research is to create and apply an effective e-marketing plan on Hilton's web site. Through this analysis, the company has used some basic marketing concepts in the website to be able to sustain in the business. It can be concluded that with development of this new brochure/ecommerce site it has opportunities to reach wide ranges of customer and helps company to increase sales. From the analysis it has been considered his study to be a successful research as he has reached his main goal, which was to make a research about the e-marketing activity and implement it in the new website. With the development of this new website Hilton is able to:

- 1) Clear information about the products and prices with attractive website design.
- 2) Make the website higher ranking in the Google.
- 3) Be able to track the customer's behaviour and buying habits and make offers accordingly.
- 4) List all customer information's and email address of customers so that they can send monthly newsletter and offer to all customer with a click.
- 5) Be able to track all activities, which help to plan marketing activities accordingly.

From the analysis it has been motivated and fully supported throughout this research process. From the analysis it has been very thankful to Hilton who has provided these opportunities and has belief in from the analysis it has been. In

this research process from the analysis it has been have chances to learn different aspects of e- marketing that can be helpful for career.

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